

PREVALENCE OF MYOPIA DISEASE IN ADOLESCENTS AND MEASURES FOR ITS PREVENTION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10988228>

Abstract. *In this article, the occurrence of myopia (nearsightedness) in adolescents and the social psychological changes that occur as a result of it. Data of 2018-2022 in the Termiz branch was conducted on the basis of retrospective analysis. It was found that the incidence is higher among residents of urbanized districts, and the ratio of male to female incidence is 3:1. Among the patients in the study, 70% had mild myopia, 20% had severe myopia, and 10% had high myopia.*

Keywords: *mild degree of myopia -1D to 2.75D, moderate degree of myopia from -3D to -5.75D, high degree of myopia -6D and above, morbidity, patient.*

Relevance of the topic: The incidence of myopia in the world is increasing day by day. According to the data of the World Health Organization (WHO), more than 140 million people are suffering from myopia. Myopia is divided into three groups (mild, moderate and high) based on physical and clinical refraction. is the type of eye adapted to the ring, divided into congenital and life-acquired types. Acquired types occur mainly among teenagers who work long hours at close range. Myopia is 25% of common eye diseases. Myopia in patients not only reduces the quality of life, but also causes a significant decrease in vision in 13-14% of cases. Myopia disease has the character of progressive growth in adolescence and is accompanied by degenerative changes in all layers of the eyeball and the central nervous system. Myopia is one of the most urgent problems of global health care, taking the 2nd place after allergic eye disease in adolescents. According to the latest report of the World Health Organization, in 2023, the number of adolescent patients with myopia will be 71 million (1% of the world's population). In Uzbekistan, the incidence of this disease was 8.2%. [2] More than 350,000 people suffer from myopia-related diseases every year. The average rate of detection of myopia among the population in Russia is from 0.1% to 0.3%. 60-70% of teenagers suffering from myopia have mild myopia, 15-20% have moderate myopia, and 7-10% have high myopia. Chronic use of social networks (Telegram, Instagram, Tik-Tok, Facebook, WhatsApp, Odnoklassniki, and YouTube) causes myopia in adolescents.

The purpose of the work: to determine the factors that cause myopia, to determine the incidence of myopia and to develop preventive measures.

Materials and methods: The 2018-2023 data were retrospectively analyzed at the Department of Ophthalmology of the Multidisciplinary Medical Hospital of Surkhondarya Region and the Termiz Branch of the Republican Eye Microsurgery Center. Research was conducted mainly based on patient anamnesis, clinical laboratory and instrumental analysis. Patients were studied in the districts of Surkhondarya region. The state of the disease, the consequences of the disease, and the frequency of meeting with age were studied.

Research results: A retrospective analysis of the ambulatory card and medical history of 162 patients with myopia at the time of death and who were under the control of the dispenser was carried out. The patients under our observation are 134 men and 28 women. According to the results of the analysis, 6-7% of patients with myopia complained of decreased visual acuity, 92-

93% of patients diagnosed as a result of preventive examination and placed under the control of the dispenser. Degenerative diseases of the eyeball and diseases of the central nervous system, as complications of myopia, have a prevalence of 1:1.4 among the urban and rural population. In our investigation, there are 2 people from Termiz city (40%), 14 people from Muzrobot district (13.3%), 15 people from Sherabad district (16.7%), 16 people from Denov district (20%), 15 people from Termiz district. In our observation, the incidence rate of men and women was 3:1. The age-specific occurrence of the disease was 16-27 years old. It was found that the disease occurs at a high level in our 20-year-old patients. By gender, 44 (71%) patients were men, 18 (29%) were women. 32 (51.6%) patients were 16-18 years old, 24 (38.7%) were 19-25 years old, 6 (9.7%) were 26-27 years old. Among them, 16-18-year-old men - 26 (59.1%), 19-24-year-old 14 (31.8%), 25-27-year-old 4 (9.1%). There were 6 (33.3%) women aged 16-18, 10 (55.6%) aged 19-25, and 2 (11.1%) aged 25-27. Myopia is divided into three levels depending on the degree of nearsightedness. We found mild myopia in 134 patients, medium myopia in 14 patients, severe myopia in 14 patients. All patients underwent biomicroscopy, visometry, side-illumination examination of the eyeball. Almost all patients complained of not being able to control the distance well. Cancer treatment was recommended to all patients with myopia, regardless of the level of the disease.

Based on the anamnestic data of the patients in our study, on the basis of questionnaires and objective, subjective and instrumental examinations, the clinical signs characteristic of myopia were determined based on the origin of the disease. In cases of myopia in adolescents, 70% of adolescents did not realize that they had the disease. They believed that everyone has the same sharpness of vision. When teenagers come to complain that the symptoms of the disease do not disappear, visual acuity is not restored even after taking conservative treatments, they do not use electronic literature for a long time, they occasionally stare into the distance, the need for small appliances in the room at night, strict personal hygiene. It was recommended that they comply. Thus, myopia is considered one of the diseases that cause a decrease in the ability to see. In modern medicine, the continuous implementation of measures aimed at preventing myopia, purposeful and orderly use of social and real life leads to a decrease in the occurrence of the disease.

Conclusion: 1. The spread and exacerbation of myopia in adolescence leads to a decrease in visual acuity, degenerative changes in the eyeball and the central nervous system.

2. Periodic and permanent specialist examinations and consultations lead to a decrease in the disease.

3. The fact that conservative treatment does not always fully help patients with myopia is expressed by the breadth of the flow of electronic information and the speed of social networks.

4. Using the eyes while using electronic literature, following a strict regime, and taking conservative treatment measures together, the activity of vision helps to improve the quality of life.

5. It is necessary to pay attention to the preliminary diagnosis in the family polyclinic eye doctor, QVP and medical consultations. It is necessary to strictly regulate the explanation of chronic eye myopia disease and its consequences to patients.

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